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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, construction is booming in most third world countries, and in particular in Congo Brazzaville. Witnesses of extreme climatic instabilities and changes (winds and temperatures), which continue to shake up the course of time and cause damage to certain civil engineering structures in Congo. These extreme values of climatic variables (winds, temperatures) present very specific challenges in terms of environmental risks. Estimating the recurrence of wind speeds and temperatures provides major information for the design of certain Civil Engineering structures, such as: buildings, bridges, roads, etc. The purpose of this paper is to calculate the normal basic and extreme dynamic pressures of the wind, as well as to establish the map of the dynamic pressure of the winds, which are taken into account in the design of civil engineering structures, in order to effectively secure and protect property and people. In this work, the data used cover a period from 1981 to 2020. The distribution law used in this work is Gumbel's law, for the estimation and calculation of normal base and extreme velocities, and of normal basic and extreme dynamic pressures, added to this, a descriptive statistic of the data on the return time period ranging from 10 to 100 years has been made, in order to assess the position and dispersion of the results between the meteorological stations concerned. And, in accordance with the NV65 snow and wind rules, the establishment of dynamic pressure maps has been done according to the French association for standardization (AFNOR). All the work has yielded satisfactory results at all the meteorological stations considered.

1. INTRODUCTION

Current climate change, its warming and its anthropogenic origin are now the subject of great concern in the community of researchers, scientists and climatologists. This atmospheric modification caused by the increase in the concentration of Greenhouse Gases, leads to temperature differences that shake and change and degrade the fabric of the atmosphere. On a global scale, we can expect an intensification and upheaval in the trends of atmospheric turbulence caused by climate change. Indeed, we can mention in particular the increase in regional disparities, the modification of seasonal cycles and an increase in the extremes of winds and temperatures. In the middle of the 21st century, the construction of civil engineering works is booming in most third world countries and in Congo Brazzaville in particular. It is a major challenge since the development of a country depends on the construction of infrastructure (buildings, bridges, ...).

Indeed, in the atmosphere, the wind is a turbulent air flow that induces a fluctuating force field on load-bearing structures, buildings and engineering structures. The latter then causes until it reaches the limit load and leads to the ruin of the structures [1]. Thus, the estimation of the recurrence of wind speeds and dynamic pressures provides essential information for the design and construction of infrastructures such as: buildings, bridges, roads, and other structures, in order to effectively protect the population and their property [2].

Statistical modelling of extreme values was done by exploring the maximum gross wind speeds of annual winds due to ease of exploitation and statistical efficiency [3], using Gumbel's law. This law is used by most official meteorological services to determine extreme climatic values: winds, rainfall, etc., [4] ; [5] ; [6]. Also, several other studies have shown the robustness of Gumbel's law in estimating extreme values [7] over the other laws. Indeed, the coherence of Gumbel's law comes from the simplicity in the application of its calculations and the geometric configuration of the plot on the linear probability scale [2]. Thus, the aim of the work is to estimate normal basic and extreme dynamic pressures, as well as to establish wind and dynamic pressure maps, for the prevention of risks related to the destabilization, instability and collapse of certain structures in Congo Brazzaville.

2. PRESENTATION OF THE STUDY AREA

2.1. Geographical Location

The Congo, in long form the Republic of the Congo or informally the Congo-Brazzaville, is a country in Central Africa, located on both sides of the equator. It covers an area of 342,000 km² and has a 170 km coastline on the Atlantic Ocean. It is bordered by Gabon to the west; Cameroon in the north-northwest; the Central African Republic to the north-northeast; the Democratic Republic of the Congo 2 to the northeast, southeast and south; Cabinda (Angola) to the southwest. The country stretches over 1500km from north to south and 425km from East to West [8].

Figure 1: administrative map of the Congo [9].

2.2. Topography

The relief of the Congo is moderate overall, with relatively low altitudes. It is essentially made up of three features, namely: plains, plateaus, hills and medium mountains.

Congo or Republic of Congo-Brazzaville is located in the Congo River sedimentary basin and on the ancient granite rocks of the old African basement that appear on the surface in the southwest. It is not located in the zone of earthquakes or volcanoes.

The plains are present in the coastal plain, the Niari valley and the Congolese Basin. The coastal plain is located between the Atlantic Ocean and the Mayombe, 50 km to 60 km wide and 170 km long. It is a sedimentary basin whose altitudes vary between 200 meters and 300 meters. The soil of this coastal plain is largely sandy. The Niari valley is a depression between the Mayombe and the Chaillu massif. The altitude of this area is around 320 meters.

The Congolese Basin is located in the north of the country. It is the western part of this great basin of Central Africa. Indeed, it forms a large amphitheater with a very gentle slope, rising to the west. It is at the same time an alluvial and sedimentary plain that is partly floodable. Its altitudes vary from 200 metres to 380 metres [10].

The Oubangian plateaus separate the Congolese Basin from the Chad Basin in the far North [11]. To the northwest, the plateaus of the Western Sangha are eroded and have hilly shapes. They are dominated by Mount Nabemba, the highest peak in Congo at 1,000 meters above sea level. In the centre, a sandy area of plateaus and hills is dominated by four plateaus including Bakukuya (450 km²), Djambala (1,250 km²), Ngo-Nsah (300 km²), and Mbé (6,500 km²) [12]. To the south, the Pool has sandy-sandstone plateaus dominated by the Cataracts plateau, the Bembé plateau and the Dondo plateau. They are all located in the south-west of the country and are the Chaillu massif and the Mayombe. The Chaillu massif, located between the Téké plateaus and the Niari valley (including part of southeastern Gabon), is a powerful granite and gneiss massif 850 metres high. Its highest point in Congo is Mount Birougou with 900 meters above sea level. The Mayombe is located between the plain Le Mayombe est situé entre la plaine côtière et la vallée du Niari. Il culmine à 850 mètres au mont Bamba et à 930 mètres au mont Mvougouti [13]. The relief (altitudes) favours the circulation of the different air masses approaching the territory.

2.3. Climate

The Congo is located entirely in the warm and humid intertropical zone between the 4th parallel north and the 5th parallel south [14]. The air masses are under the subordination of anticyclones [15]. From the two anticyclones, Saharan and South African, are born masses of hot and dry air that flow westwards, while the Saint Helena anticyclone directs warm and humid air to the east and northeast that penetrates into the interior of the country.

As it progresses, the Atlantic air meets the warm and dry air of the Indian Ocean [16].

In the southwest of the country, the relief units are parallel to each other and from northwest to southeast. In the north and centre, the west is raised and the east is made up of a depression. This allows for good air circulation and precipitation.[17] The vegetation, composed of forests and savannahs, has a high relative humidity.

2.3.1. Climate characteristics

The average temperature of the Congo is 25 °C. The temperature amplitudes are small; they fluctuate from 2°C to 3°C. The air is always humid. [18]. Rainfall is around 1,600 mm per year with maximums in March-April and October-November.

2.3.2. Types of climates

Recent works by Samba and Nganga (2011) have shown that long series of climatic data subdivide the Congo into two types of climates: the equatorial climate of the north and the humid tropical climate of the south.

2.3.2.1. The Equatorial Climate

The hot and humid equatorial climate concerns the north of the country, particularly for the departments of Likouala, Sangha, the north of Cuvette-Ouest and Cuvette centrale. The average temperature is 26 °C with abundant rainfall all year round, from 1,800 mm to 2,000 mm per year. The dry season is almost absent. The temperature range is 2 °C.

2.3.2.2. The Humid Tropical Climate

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[16]

The humid tropical climate concerns the south of the country, as well as the north of the pool and part of the plateau department, from the Atlantic coast to Brazzaville. The average temperature is 25 °C with rainfall of 1,200 mm to 1,600 mm per year. There are two seasons, the temperature range is 5 °C. This climate is under the preponderant influence of intertropical low pressure from October to May and southern subtropical high pressure from June to September, the intertropical convergent cloud cover (ITCZ) is reversed while directly influencing solar radiation and insolation. It is also characterized by an alternation of two seasons, including a rainy and hot season that runs from November to April and a cool season that runs from June to September.

2.3.3. Climate Impacts

The high rainfall and temperature maintain a lush tropical flora; the Congo Basin forest is the second largest forest in the world [19]. There are also savannahs [20]. The fauna includes several species such as gorilla, chimpanzee, elephant, hippopotamus, buffalo, pangolin... for the development of the tourism industry.

The rains feed an abundant hydrography that makes the Congo a hydromorphic country. The important rivers are, in addition to the Congo River, the Nkény and the Alima [21]. This rainy climate allows the soil to be watered, but it is degraded by leaching [22] and by the formation of shells, making it difficult for plants to germinate.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Materials

The climatic data (wind and temperature) used in our study were obtained through the National Civil Aviation Agency (ANAC) through the National Meteorological Directorate. These are wind speed and temperature data collected in nine (09) weather stations in Congo Brazzaville. These data cover a period from 1981 to 2020. The processing of the data for this study required the use of software such as: Excel, RStudio, to perform calculations and graphs and to obtain box plots.

3.2. Methods

For our study, we collected wind and temperature data from nine (9) main weather stations, at the National Civil Aviation Agency through the National Directorate of Meteorology. The stations considered are located in the following localities: Brazzaville, Pointe-Noire, Impfondo, Dolisie, Ouessou, Makoua, Djambala, Sibiti, Mouyondzi. Their geographical coordinates and number of years of observations are given in Table I.

Table I: geographical coordinates and duration of years of observations of the meteorological stations of Congo Brazzaville

Weather stations	Localization		Altitude (m)	Period of years of observations	Duration of years of observations
	Latitude	Longitude			
Brazzaville	4.25°S	15.25°E	319	1981-2020	40 years
Pointe-Noire	4.82°S	11.90°E	17	1981-2020	40 years
Impfondo	1.62°N	18.07°E	335	1981-2020	40 years
Dolisie	-4.2°N	12.7°E	390	1981-2020	40 years
Ouessou	1.62°N	16.05°E	352	1981-2020	40 years
Makoua	0.02°S	15.58°E	394	1981-2020	40 years
Djambala	-2.53°S	14.76°E	791	1981-2020	40 years
Sibiti	3.68°S	13.35°E	530	1981-2020	40 years
Mouyondzi	3.98°S	13.92°E	509	1981-2020	40 years

Hourly average wind speeds are measured using an anemometer at the nine (9) weather stations. Average hourly speeds are analyzed using the Canadian Standard (NBC) which is a method based on the analysis of maximum mean hourly speeds [23], [24]. Thus, from the reference wind speeds, we identified the maximum annual speeds of each weather station. Also, an analysis of the temperatures of the nine (09) weather stations made it possible to obtain the average temperatures that were used to calculate the air density at the level of each weather station. Before the qualitative and quantitative analysis of wind speeds, the rules first recommend their normalization at a height of 10m above the ground, hence the expression:

$$\frac{V_H}{V_{10}} = \left(\frac{H}{10}\right)^{\frac{1}{7}} \tag{1}$$

With:

V_H (m/s) means the wind speed measured by an anemometer at height H above the ground.

V_{10} (m/s), the reference speed measured at the reference height H_0 .

H (m/s) height at each weather station.

3.2.1. Exploratory analysis of the data from the different Stations

In this section, it was a question of making an exploratory analysis of the data of the nine (09) meteorological stations concerned, in order to verify and assess the quality of the data collected in the following regions: Brazzaville, Pointe-Noire, Impfondo, Dolisie, Ouessou, Makoua, Djambala, Sibiti, Mouyondzi.

3.2.2. Presentation and modelling of the law used

3.2.2.1. Justification

For this statistical modelling, we considered the maximum gross annual wind speeds for the estimation of normal base speeds and extreme speeds, and the annual mean temperatures for the determination of normal basic dynamic pressures and extreme dynamic pressures, at the level of each year over the period studied, due to their simplicity of application and their effectiveness in the statistical field (HABIBI *et al.* 2013), using Gumbel's law, which has shown its robustness in estimating extreme values in several works [7].

3.2.2.2. Presentation

It is a law of exponential decrease, it adjusts, for durations of 1 hour to a few days, on the maximums of 10 to 15 days, monthly maximums, seasonal maximums or annual maximums. Its advantage is to stretch the distribution scale to a probability beyond 0.90. It is also a doubly exponential function, whose distribution function is:

$$F(x) = \exp \left[-\exp \left(-\frac{x-a}{b} \right) \right] \tag{2}$$

Where a and b denote the position and scale parameters, respectively.

3.2.2.3. Modelling Gumbel's Law

The reference velocity (V_r), denoted x is calculated by means of Gumbel's law, represented by the following equation [25]:

$$x = a - b \ln \left[-\ln \left(\frac{1}{1-T_r} \right) \right] \tag{3}$$

a , and b represent the Gumbel parameters and are calculated by the moment method, which consists of equating samples with theoretical moments of the distribution.

$$\begin{cases} \hat{a} = \mu - \hat{b}\gamma \\ \hat{b} = \frac{\sqrt{6}}{\pi}\sigma \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

With
$$\mu = \frac{\sum_i^n x_i}{n} \tag{6}$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i^n (x_i - \mu)^2}{N}} \tag{7}$$

$\hat{a}$ = position parameter estimated by the method of moments

$\hat{b}$ = Scale parameter estimated by the method of moments

μ = The average

σ = Standard deviation

γ = 0.5772 (Euler's constant)

3.2.3. Calculation of speeds

Basic normal speeds and extreme speeds are calculated in accordance with the snow and wind rules NV65. The results obtained are presented in Appendix 3 and are based on a study carried out in previous work [25].

3.2.4. Dynamic pressures from wind and temperature analysis

3.2.4.1. Basic Normal Dynamic Pressure

The basic normal dynamic pressure (N/m²) is established by applying Bernouilli's theorem from the normal base velocity [26]:

$$q_{nb} = \frac{1}{2} \rho v_{bn}^2 \quad (13)$$

As for the density, it is equal to:

$$\rho = \frac{P}{rT} \quad (14)$$

From (1) et (2), we have:

And :

$$T = 273 + t \quad (15)$$

With :

ρ : The density of the air.

r= The mass constant of air considered as an ideal gas, its value is: The mass constant of air considered as an ideal gas, its value is:

r = 287 J/Kg.°K

P = 101325 Pa

T= air temperature in °K, its expression is

T= 273+t

t is the air temperature in °C.

3.2.4.2. Extreme Dynamic Pressure

The extreme dynamic pressure is given by the following relationship:

$$q_e = 1.75q_{nb} \quad (16)$$

3.2.5. Descriptive Statistics

In this part, we are interested in analyzing a table with the values of the basic normal dynamic pressures (q_{nb}) and the extreme dynamic pressures (q_e) at nine sites as a function of the return time period ranging from 10 to 100 years. We start with a small descriptive analysis by giving a statistical summary including calculating the descriptive statistics for each site, such as the mean, standard deviation, quartiles, for the minimum and maximum values. We will give the box plots to visualize the distribution of dynamic pressures for each site.

3.2.6. Establishment of Wind and Dynamic Pressure Charts

The establishment of the wind map and that of dynamic pressures was done in analogy with the case of France, in accordance with the French Association for Standardization and the snow and wind rules (NV 65).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Interpretation of the Results

From this exploratory analysis, it appears that in some meteorological stations there was a lack of wind speed data. These have been logically supplemented, either by the median or by the mean of the series, when the data from the said meteorological station follow a normal distribution or not. This analysis allowed us to understand the distribution of wind and temperature data at each weather station.

From the determination of the Gumbel parameters, and the modeling of this law, we have calculated the reference velocities for each meteorological station with a return time of 100 years at regular intervals of 10 years, with. These values allowed us to calculate extreme speeds and normal base speeds or gust wind speeds at each weather station. The results are represented in the table below.

An analysis of the temperatures of the nine (9) weather stations provided the average air temperatures and densities that were used to calculate the air density at each station (Table III).

Table II: Average temperatures and air density

	Weather stations								
	Brazzaville	Pointe-Noire	Impfondo	Ouessou	Dolisie	Djambala	Sibiti	Mouyondzi	Makoua
Year of observation	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020
Observation period	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years
Average temperatures	32.78	31.63	33.37	33.41	32.75	30.06	30.45	30.69	32.57
Air density	1.15	1.16	1.15	1.15	1.15	1.16	1.16	1.16	1.16

The analysis of air temperatures and densities allowed us to calculate the normal basic and extreme dynamic pressures of the weather stations concerned, with a return time of 100 years, at regular intervals of 10 years. Table IV presents the results obtained.

Table III: Extreme and normal basic dynamic wind pressures, as a function of the return time at each weather station

	Weather stations									
	Brazzaville	Pointe-Noire	Impfondo	Ouessou	Dolisie	Djambala	Sibiti	Mouyondzi	Makoua	
Year of observation	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	
Observation of period	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	
10	q_{nb}	7.42	11.44	3.52	1.47	5.98	4.01	1.78	1.96	2.72
	q_e	12.98	20.01	6.16	2.57	10.46	7.02	3.12	3.43	4.75

20	q_{nb}	7.77	12.25	4.98	1.63	7.30	4.59	2.24	2.27	3.08
	q_e	13.60	21.44	8.71	2.85	12.78	8.04	3.92	3.98	5.39
30	q_{nb}	7.95	12.63	5.77	1.68	7.89	4.87	2.47	2.44	3.27
	q_e	13.92	22.11	10.1	2.95	13.81	8.53	4.33	4.27	5.73
40	q_{nb}	8.08	12.86	6.24	1.74	8.32	5.07	2.61	2.54	3.39
	q_e	14.13	22.51	10.9	3.04	14.56	8.87	4.57	4.45	5.94
50	q_{nb}	8.14	13.02	6.62	1.77	8.63	5.16	2.72	2.61	3.51
	q_e	14.24	22.78	11.6	3.09	15.11	9.04	4.75	4.57	6.14
60	q_{nb}	8.21	13.17	6.90	1.81	8.89	5.26	2.79	2.64	3.55
	q_e	14.35	23.05	12.1	3.14	15.55	9.21	4.88	4.63	6.22
70	q_{nb}	8.26	13.25	7.19	1.83	9.08	5.36	2.86	2.72	3.63
	q_e	14.45	23.19	12.6	3.21	15.89	9.38	5.00	4.75	6.34
80	q_{nb}	8.26	13.33	7.36	1.83	9.21	5.41	2.93	2.75	3.68
	q_e	14.45	23.33	12.9	3.21	16.12	9.47	5.13	4.81	6.43
90	q_{nb}	8.32	13.41	7.54	1.85	9.34	5.51	2.97	2.79	3.72
	q_e	14.56	23.47	13.2	3.25	16.35	9.65	5.21	4.88	6.50
100	q_{nb}	8.32	13.49	7.71	1.85	9.47	5.56	3.00	2.79	3.76
	q_e	14.56	23.61	13.5	3.25	16.58	9.74	5.26	4.88	6.58

From this table, we plot boxes to give more visualization on the variability of normal and extreme dynamic pressures.

Figure 2 provides information on the normal dynamic pressure base values of the winds from the nine weather stations. It can be seen that in Brazzaville, Pointe-Noire and Impfondo, the normal dynamic base wind pressure varies from 7.42 N/m² to 8.32 N/m² respectively; from 11.44 N/m² to 13.49 N/m² and from 3.52 N/m² to 7.71 N/m²; from 1.47 N/m² to 1.85 N/m² in Ouesso; from 5.98 N/m² to 9.47 N/m² in Dolisie; from 4.01 N/m² to 5.56 N/m² in Djambala; from 1.78 N/m² to 3.00 N/m² in Sibiti, from 1.96 N/m² to 2.79 N/m² in Mouyondzi and from 2.72 N/m² to 3.76 N/m² in Makoua. As for Figure 3, it shows the extreme dynamic pressure values of the winds, we note that in Brazzaville, Pointe-Noire and Impfondo, the extreme dynamic pressure varies respectively from 12.98 N/m² to 14.56 N/m²; from 20.01 N/m² to 23.61 N/m² and from 6.16 N/m² to 13.5 N/m²; in Ouesso it varies from 2.57 N/m² to 3.52 N/m²; in Dolisie from 10.46 N/m² to 16.58 N/m²; from 7.02 N/m² to 9.74 N/m² in Djambala; from 3.12 N/m² to 5.26 N/m² in Sibiti, from 3.43 N/m² to 4.88 N/m² in Mouyondzi and from 4.75 N/m² to 6.58 N/m² in Makoua.

Figure 2: Variability of normal dynamic baseline wind pressures from the Nine weather stations

Figure 3: Variability of Dynamic Wind Pressures from the Nine Weather Stations

[Mangla *al.*, 13(11): November, 2024]
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Figure 4 gives an overview of the values of normal baseline or gust dynamic pressures at all weather stations, with a return time of 50 years. It shows us that the wind speed is much higher in Pointe-Noire with a value of 13.02 N/m², then in Dolisie with 8.63 N/m², in Brazzaville with 8.13 N/m², in Impfondo with 6.62 N/m², in Djambala with 5.16 N/m², in Makoua with 3.51 N/m², in Sibiti with 2.72 N/m², and finally in Mouyondzi with a value of 2.61 N/m².

N/m², in Djambala with 5.16 N/m², in Makoua with 3.51 N/m², in Sibiti with 2.72 N/m², and finally in Mouyondzi with a value of 2.61 N/m².

As for Figure 5, it shows the values of the extreme dynamic pressures of the winds, obtained at each weather station with a return time of 50 years. It is clearly noticeable that in Pointe-Noire, the extreme wind speed is higher than in other meteorological stations with a value of 22.78 N/m², 15.11 N/m² in Dolisie, 14.23 N/m² in Brazzaville, 11.59 N/m² in Impfondo, 9.04 N/m² in Djambala, 6.15 N/m² in Makoua, 4.75 N/m² in Sibiti and 4.57 N/m² in Mouyondzi.

Figure 4: Basic normal dynamic pressures with a return time of 50 years

Figure 5: Extreme dynamic pressures with a 50-year payback time

After calculating the basic normal dynamic pressures and the extreme dynamic pressures, we calculated descriptive statistics for each weather station, which are shown in Table IV.

Table IV: descriptive statistics of basic and extreme normal dynamic pressures as a function of the return time ranging from 10 years to 100 years.

Weather stations	Brazzaville	Pointe-Noire	Impfondo	Ouesso	Dolisie	Djambala	Sibiti	Makoua	Mouyondzi
Basic Normal Average	8.07	12.89	6.38	1.74	8.41	5.08	2.64	3.43	2.55
Extreme average	14.12	22.55	11.17	3.05	14.72	8.89	4.62	6.00	4.46
Basic Normal Standard deviation	0.29	0.64	1.32	0.12	1.09	0.48	0.38	0.33	0.26
Extreme Standard deviation	0.50	1.11	2.30	0.21	1.91	0.84	0.67	0.57	0.46

It therefore emerges from this descriptive analysis that over the period of the return time from 10 to 100 years, in Brazzaville we have a normal basic mean $\mu_{nb} = 8.07$, an extreme mean $\mu_e = 14.12$, a normal standard deviation of the base $\sigma_{nb} = 0.29$, an extreme standard deviation $\sigma_e = 0.50$; In Pointe-Noire with a normal mean of base $\mu_{nb} = 12.89$, an extreme mean $\mu_e = 22.55$, a normal standard deviation of the base $\sigma_{nb} = 0.64$, an extreme standard deviation $\sigma_e = 1.11$; a normal basic mean $\mu_{nb} = 6.38$, an extreme mean $\mu_e = 11.17$, a normal basic standard deviation $\sigma_{nb} = 1.32$, an extreme standard deviation $\sigma_e = 2.30$, at Impfondo; In Ouesso, a normal basic mean $\mu_{nb} = 1.74$, an extreme mean $\mu_e = 3.05$, a normal basic standard deviation $\sigma_{nb} = 0.12$, an extreme standard deviation $\sigma_e = 0.21$; At Dolisie, a normal basic mean $\mu_{nb} = 8.41$, an extreme mean $\mu_e = 14.72$, a normal basic standard deviation $\sigma_{nb} = 1.09$, an extreme standard deviation $\sigma_e = 1.91$; a normal mean of base $\mu_{nb} = 5.08$, an extreme mean $\mu_e = 8.89$, a normal standard deviation of base $\sigma_{nb} = 0.48$, an extreme standard deviation $\sigma_e = 0.84$, at Djambala; At Sibiti we have, a normal basic mean $\mu_{nb} = 2.64$, an extreme mean $\mu_e = 4.62$, a normal basic standard deviation $\sigma_{nb} = 0.38$, an extreme standard deviation $\sigma_e = 0.67$; In Makoua, a normal basic mean $\mu_{nb} = 3.43$, an extreme mean $\mu_e = 6.00$, a normal basic standard deviation $\sigma_{nb} = 0.33$, an extreme standard deviation $\sigma_e = 0.57$; and finally at Mouyondzi, a normal basic mean $\mu_{nb} = 2.55$, an extreme mean $\mu_e = 4.46$, a normal standard deviation of the base $\sigma_e = 0.26$, an extreme standard deviation $\sigma_{nb} = 0.46$.

Table V: Dispersion of dynamic pressures around the mean (basic normal and extreme) over a return period ranging from 10 to 100 years

Weather stations	Brazzaville	Pointe-Noire	Impfondo	Ouesso	Dolisie	Djambala	Sibiti	Makoua	Mouyondzi
Basic Normal Average	5.69								
Extreme average	9.96								
Basic Normal Standard Deviation	0.29	0.64	1.32	0.12	1.09	0.48	0.38	0.33	0.26
extreme standard deviation	0.50	1.11	2.30	0.21	1.91	0.84	0.67	0.57	0.46

From this table, we compare the dispersion of the dynamic pressures of each weather station around the mean (basic normal and extreme). We find that at Mouyondzi, the data are closer around the basic normal mean with a base normal standard deviation equal to 0.26 and around the extreme mean with an extreme standard deviation equal to 0.46, than at all other meteorological stations that have basic normal standard deviations equal to 0.57; 0.67 ; 0.84 ; 1.91 ; 0.21 ; 2.30 ; and extreme equal to 0.57; 0.67 ; 0.84 ; 1.91 ; 0.21 ; 2.30 ; 1.11 ; 0.50, respectively for the two cases, in Makoua, Sibiti, Djambala, Dolisie, Ouesso, Impfondo, Pointe-Noire, and Brazzaville. These results are in accordance with those found in Table V, where it can be seen that the data of the dynamic pressures (basic normal and extreme) at Mouyondzi are more grouped around its two means, respectively the basic normal and extreme average; than in the case of other weather stations, around their averages (basic normal and extreme).

Each administrative block, department, where the meteorological station is located, is made up of several localities, which are classified in the table below:

Table VI: Departments and their localities

Departments (Weather concerned) stations	localities
Brazzaville/ Pool (Brazzaviile)	Brazzaville, Kintélé, Kinkala Boko, Goma Tsé-Tsé, Ignié Kimba, Kindamba, Louingui, Loumo, Mayama, Mbandza-Ndonga, Mindouli, Ngabé Vindza
Pointe-Noire/ Kouilou (Pointe-Noire)	Pointe-Noire, Loango, Hinda, Kakamoéka, Madingo-Kayes Mvouti, Nzambi
Likouala (Impfondo)	Impfondo, Bétou, Bouanéla, Dongou, Enyellé Epeéna, liranga
Sangha (Ouesso)	Ouesso, kabo Mokeko, Ngbala, Pikounda, Sembé, Souanké, Pokola
Cuvette ouest/ Cuvette (Makoua)	Owando, Boundji, Bokoma, Loukolela, Makoua, Mossaka, Ngoko Ntokou, Oyo, Tchikapika, Ewo, Etoumbi, Kellé Mbama, Mbomo Okoyo
Plateaux (Djambala)	Djambala, Gamboma, Abala Allembé, Lékana, Makotipoko, Mbon Mpouya, Ngo Ollombo, Ongogni
Bouenza (Mouyondzi)	Madingou, Boko-songho, Kayes kingoué, Loudima, Mabombo, Mfouati, Mouyondzi, tsiaki Yamba, Nkayi
Lekoumou (Sibiti)	Sibiti, Mayéyé, Komono, Bambama, Zanaga
Niari (Dolisie)	Dolisie, Banda Divenié, Kibangou, Kimongo, Londéya-Kaye, Louvakou, Makabana, Mayoko, Mbinda, Mougoundou-Sud, Mougoundou-Nord, Moutamba, Nyanga Yaya, Mossendjo

For reasons of hardness, the snow and wind rules (NV 65) recommend working with a payback time of 50 years. The values represented in the maps are those that have been retained with a return time of 50 years, on all the meteorological stations concerned.

After drawing up the maps of the dynamic pressures, we notice on Appendices 1 and 2 that on Pointe-Noire the normal basic dynamic pressures and the extreme dynamic pressures are higher than on other meteorological stations, this is due to the fact that Pointe-Noire is a city close to the sea and exposed to sea winds. And we also notice that at the Ouessou weather station we have values of basic normal dynamic pressures and very low extreme dynamic pressures, because it is a city characterized by the presence of a lot of trees, which disturb the flow of wind.

In view of the results obtained in the various meteorological stations concerned, the values made it possible to graph the zones of influence of the dynamic pressures (Annex 1) as well as that of the consolidated map (Annex 2) which suggests a distribution of extreme dynamic pressures and normal basic dynamic pressures into four zones of influence.

In sum, we observe a periodic variability of extreme dynamic pressures and basic normal dynamic pressures, with strong and low values.

5. Discussion

Congo-Brazzaville is animated by a significant and incessant variability of winds which influences dynamic pressures (normal base and extreme). Nevertheless, there is a very significant difference between the maximum values for the dynamic pressure data of the Kouilou Pointe-Noire; ($q_{nb} = 13.02 \text{ N/m}^2$ and $q_e = 22.78 \text{ N/m}^2$) considered as maximum values and the Sangha – Ouessou zone ($q_{nb} = 1.77 \text{ N/m}^2$ and $q_e = 3.09 \text{ N/m}^2$), these minimum values are justified by the geographical location, climate, relief and vegetation. On the other hand, the preponderance of wind speeds in the Kouilou-Pointe-Noire area is essentially explained by the quasi-permanent establishment of a sea breeze regime which is reflected in the fact that low pressure relative to the ground is frequent there, in this case by the warm air observed [26]; [6].

There is also a strong presence of currents (superficial and its Gabon-Congo current) of the continental shelf in front of the city of Pointe-Noire, which have a great influence on the flow and wind speeds [27], and which in turn directly impact the dynamic pressures in this area.

In several countries of the world, some research work has already been carried out in the context of the determination of dynamic pressures with a view to adapting aerodynamic and aeroelastic conditions [28] ; [29] ; [30]. However, in Africa, with the exception of the Maghreb countries (North Africa), little work has been undertaken in Sub-Saharan Africa [31]. Almost all data on wind stresses, in this case dynamic pressures, on civil engineering structures are based on the French Snow and Wind Regulation (1965, 1999) and is the one used by most professionals in the construction trades. This certainly poses problems of optimization and oversizing of structures. Nevertheless, wind speeds depend a lot, on climatic factors, the environment, the relief of each area. The results concerning the calculation of the normal basic and extreme dynamic pressures in the framework of this work are consistent with those obtained in the work of [23];[26];[27];[28];[29];[30];[31] ; [32] et [33].

However, given the geographical location of the Congo, we note that the results obtained in the framework of this work are much lower than those of the data on dynamic pressures (basic normal and extreme) which appear in the French regulation (NV, 1965, 1999) or in the Maghreb countries.

6. Conclusion

The main interest of this work was to estimate and calculate the basic and extreme normal values of dynamic pressures, as well as to establish the maps of dynamic pressures. These values are essential in the design of civil engineering structures. In short, the results obtained are satisfactory and present a good perspective in the world of Civil Engineering in Congo Brazzaville.

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Annex 1

Figure 4: Map of the expression zones of the normal dynamic pressures of the base q_{nb} and the extreme dynamic pressures q_e

Annex 2

Figure 5: Grouping of the zones of influence and consolidation map of the normal basic dynamic pressures q_{nb} and the extreme dynamic pressures q_e

Annex 3

Table VII: Extreme and basic normal speeds in m/s, as a function of the return time at each weather station

		Weather stations									
		Brazzaville	Pointe-Noire	Impfondo	Ouessou	Dolisie	Djambala	Sibiti	Mouyondzi	Makoua	
Year of observation		1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	1981-2020	
Observation period		40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	40 years	
Return Time	10	V _{nb}	3.59	4.44	2.48	1.61	3.22	2.63	1.75	1.84	2.16
		V _e	6.29	7.77	4.33	2.81	5.64	4.60	3.07	3.22	3.79
	20	V _{nb}	3.68	4.60	2.94	1.68	3.56	2.81	1.97	1.98	2.31
		V _e	6.44	8.04	5.15	2.95	6.24	4.92	3.44	3.46	4.03
	30	V _{nb}	3.72	4.66	3.17	1.71	3.71	2.91	2.06	2.05	2.38
		V _e	6.51	8.17	5.54	2.99	6.48	5.07	3.61	3.59	4.16
	40	V _{nb}	3.75	4.71	3.30	1.74	3.80	2.96	2.12	2.09	2.42
		V _e	6.56	8.24	5.77	3.04	6.66	5.17	3.71	3.66	4.23
	50	V _{nb}	3.76	4.74	3.39	1.75	3.87	2.98	2.16	2.12	2.46
		V _e	6.58	8.29	5.94	3.07	6.78	5.22	3.79	3.71	4.31
	60	V _{nb}	3.78	4.77	4.46	1.77	3.93	3.01	2.19	2.14	2.47
		V _e	6.61	8.34	6.03	3.09	6.88	5.27	3.84	3.74	4.33
	70	V _{nb}	3.79	4.78	3.54	1.78	3.97	3.04	2.22	2.16	2.50
		V _e	6.63	8.37	6.19	3.12	6.95	5.32	3.89	3.79	4.38
	80	V _{nb}	3.79	4.79	3.58	1.78	4.00	3.05	2.25	2.18	2.52
		V _e	6.63	8.39	6.26	3.12	7.00	5.35	3.94	3.81	4.41
	90	V _{nb}	3.80	4.81	3.62	1.81	4.03	3.08	2.26	2.19	2.53
		V _e	6.66	8.41	6.34	3.14	7.05	5.41	3.96	3.84	4.43
	100	V _{nb}	3.80	4.82	3.66	1.81	4.06	3.11	2.28	2.19	2.55
		V _e	6.66	8.44	6.41	3.14	7.10	5.42	3.98	3.84	4.45